

The Development of Speaking Using Folk Tales Based On Performance Activities for Early Childhood Student

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II. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

This research aimed to

1. Study and analyze the development of speaking skill of early childhood students
2. Evaluate the development of speaking skill of early childhood students before and after speaking activities.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Concept of Speaking

For many years people taught speaking by having students repeat words, sentences and recite memorized textbook dialogues. Speaking is an interactive process of constructing meaning that involves producing and receiving and processing information [3]. Its form and meaning are dependent on the context in which it occurs, including the participants themselves, their collective experiences, the physical environment, and the purposes for speaking. It is often spontaneous, open-ended, and evolving. However, speech is not always unpredictable. Language functions (or patterns) that tend to recur in certain discourse situations (e.g., declining an invitation or requesting time off from work), can be identified and charted [4]. Furthermore; teachers should monitor learners' speech production to determine what skills and knowledge they already have and what areas need development, offering suggestions for activities that can address different skills [5]. Conclusion; speaking is key to communication. By considering what good speakers do, what speaking tasks can be used in class, and what specific needs learners report, teachers can help learners improve their speaking and overall oral competency. [6] Additionally, different people have different types of speaking voice. The tone and manner of speaking well can be developed through working out [7].

A speaker's skills and speech habits have an impact on the success of any exchange. Speakers must be able to anticipate and then produce the expected patterns of specific discourse situations. They must also manage discrete elements such as turn-taking, rephrasing, providing feedback, or redirecting. The learner must also choose the correct vocabulary to describe the item sought, rephrase or emphasize words to clarify the description [5]. Other skills and knowledge that instruction might address include the following: producing the sounds, stress patterns, rhythmic structures, and intonations of the language; using grammar structures accurately; assessing characteristics of the target audience, including shared knowledge or shared points of reference, status and power relations of participants, interest levels, or differences in

Abstract—The research on the development of speaking using folk tales based on performance activities aimed to (1) study the development of speaking skill for early- childhood students, and (2) evaluate the development of speaking skill before and after speaking activities. Ten students of Kindergarten level 2, who have enrolled in the subject of the research for speaking development of semester 2 in 2013 were purposively selected as the research cohort. The research tools were lesson plans for speaking activities and pre-post test for speaking development that were approved as content validity and reliability (IOC=.66-1.00, $\alpha=0.967$). The research found that the development of speaking skill of the research samples before using performance activities on folk tales in developing speaking skill was in the normal high level. Additionally, the results appeared that the preschoolers after applying speaking skill on performance activities also imaginatively created their speaking skill.

Keywords—Speaking development, folk tales, performance activities, early-childhood students.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE educational reform movement in Thailand is setting ambitious goals for students learning and educational quality, starting in school at the age of 3. Many factors affecting the success of educational reform contribute to achieving the goals. However, the research has shown the basis of high educational quality ultimately relied on teachers. (1) Teachers with effective teaching quality seem to be the most important factors in raising both student achievement and educational quality.

Learning language should begin in early childhood (2-5 year-old child) which developing in language skills are rapidly and effectively imitated, furthermore; their skills are regarded as the basis for lifelong learning. Speaking in early childhood is the most important; it enables children to master content and extend their learning skills in higher level, becoming more self-assured as well as creative [1].

According to Tuntiplashewa [2], a professional teacher, said that children's learning language depends on their interest, reaction with others and environment. Children start their listening, imitate what they have heard, regarding to speaking, conversation and telling story. Development in language learning at early age is a continuous process, therefore speaking skill relates to learning in the future.

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perspectives; selecting vocabulary that is understandable and appropriate for the audience, the topic being discussed, and the setting in which the speech act occurs; applying strategies to enhance comprehensibility, such as emphasizing key words, rephrasing, or checking for listener comprehension; using gestures or body language; and paying attention to the success of the interaction and adjusting components of speech such as vocabulary, rate of speech, and complexity of grammar structures to maximize listener comprehension and involvement.

B. Concept of Role Playing

- Role-playing refers to the changing of one's behavior to assume a role, either unconsciously to fill a social role, or consciously to act out an adopted role. In the other hand; role-playing refers to the changing of one's behavior to fulfill a social role", [7] in the field of psychology, the term is used more loosely in four senses:
- To refer to the playing of roles generally such as in a theatre, or educational setting;
- To refer to taking a role of an existing character or person and acting it out with a partner taking someone else's role, often involving different genres of practice;
- To refer to a wide range of games including role-playing video game, play-by-mail games and more;
- To refer specifically to role-playing games [5].

In speaking of play and its role in the preschooler's development, concerned with two fundamental questions: first, how to play itself arises in development — its origin and genesis; second, the role of this developmental activity, which we call play, as a form of development in the child of preschool age. The play the leading form of activity for a child of this age, it is simply the predominant form of speaking [8].

C. Concept of Storytelling

Storytelling predated any other form of oral history; stories have been used for centuries. Storytelling predates writing, with the earliest forms of storytelling usually oral combined with gestures and expressions. In addition to being part of religious ritual, rock art may have served as a form of storytelling for many ancient cultures [9]. Modern storytelling has a broad purview. In addition to its traditional forms, folktales, mythology, legends, fables etc.) [10], [11], it has extended fairytales itself to representing history, personal narrative, political commentary, and evolving cultural norms.

Contemporary storytelling is also widely used to address educational objectives. [12]. New forms of media are creating new ways for people to record, express, and consume stories. Tools for asynchronous group communication can provide an environment for individuals to reframe or recast individual stories into group stories. [13].

D. Conceptual Framework

First, the experimental students will be examined through the 20 –items pretest on understanding meaning of pictures.

Next, performance learning activities applied the model of storytelling to the experimental students to the possible level of listening and speaking development.

Finally, the results of the students' practices (posttest scores selection, filter and relevant evaluation) related to the development ability of speaking were analyzed.

IV. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Cohort

Ten students of Kindergarten level 2, who have enrolled in the subject of research for speaking development of semester 2 in 2013 were purposively selected as the research cohort.

B. Research Tools

The research tools were lesson plans for speaking activities pre-post test for speaking skill development that were approved as content validity and reliability (IOC=.66-1.00,0.967).

C. Data Collection

1. Pretest was taken to the ten preschoolers purposively selected from Kindergarten level 2.
2. Lesson plans of speaking activities on performance of storytelling and role plays required 24 learning periods (see Table I) were used as the way to increase of the development the students' ability on speaking skill.
3. Posttest was taken after speaking activities; data were summarized and interpreted into comprehensible results. Achievement level rating scale was used to describe the success that the experimental students have achieved and developed the ability on speaking skill.

TABLE I
 THE DEVELOPMENT RESULTS OF THE STUDENTS' ABILITY IN SPEAKING

Speaking Activities	Scores			
	total	\bar{X}	S.D.	%
Week 1	10	8.14	3.51	78.67
Week 2	10	7.64	.494	73.67
Week 3	10	8.38	.561	81.00
Week 4	10	8.72	.528	84.33
Week 5	10	8.55	.632	82.67
Week 6	10	8.17	.468	79.00
Week 7	10	9.03	.499	87.33
Week 8	10	8.37	.199	81.00
total	80	8.38	.470	81.33

V. RESULT

1. Before using speaking activities applied on performance of storytelling and role plays for developing speaking skill, the researcher investigated achievement of the ten experimental students doing 20 items pretest and found that the preschoolers had already required speaking skill. The investigation revealed that they lacked speaking skill.
2. After using speaking activities applied on performance of storytelling and role plays for developing speaking skill, the posttest was taken; the preschoolers were agreed finding out their achievement had increased which related

to gaining more knowledge and understanding concerning the process of speaking activities on performance of storytelling and role plays for developing speaking skill. (See Table II.)

TABLE II
THE DEVELOPMENT RESULTS OF THE STUDENTS' ABILITY IN SPEAKING

Speaking	Pretest		Posttest		total		
	\bar{X}	S.D.	\bar{X}	S.D.	\bar{D}	S.D.	%
1.Words	11.30	.949	17.20	.632	5.90	.568	17.20
2.Sentences	21.30	3.199	34.10	1.035	12.80	1.619	34.10
3.Stories	22.30	1.889	34.50	2.635	12.20	1.814	34.50
total	54.90	4.358	85.80	5.789	30.90	2.079	85.80

Results of the preschoolers' development on speaking skill (See Table III)

TABLE III
THE DEVELOPMENT RESULTS OF THE STUDENTS' ABILITY IN SPEAKING

Speaking	N = 10	Pretest		Posttest		\bar{D}	S.D.	t	p
		\bar{X}	S.D.	\bar{X}	S.D.				
1.Words	Pretest	11.30	.949			5.90	.568	32.868	.000*
	Posttest	17.20	.632						
2.Sentences	Pretest	21.30	3.199			12.80	1.619	24.996	.000*
	Posttest	34.10	1.035						
3.Stories	Pretest	22.30	1.889			12.20	1.814	21.273	.000*
	Posttest	34.50	2.635						
total	Pretest	54.90	4.358			30.90	2.079	47.001	.000*
	Posttest	85.80	5.789						

3. The research finding on learning on speaking activities, the satisfaction of the students was discovered that learning satisfaction could influence and motivate in learning of speaking skill. In the other hand, the students were satisfied with participating in learning activities applied on performance in role plays and storytelling. (See Table IV)

TABLE IV
EARLY CHILDHOOD' SATISFACTION TOWARD LEARNING ACTIVITY

Item	μ	σ	Level
1. I always enjoy stories.	5.00	.00	very high
2. I always read stories in my free time.	5.00	.00	very high
3. Pictures in the stories make me happy.	4.29	.71	high
4. I always follow the story until the end.	4.06	.78	high
5. I am keen on the speaking activities.	4.62	.70	high
6. I participate in role plays.	4.52	.50	very high
7. I participate in role plays.	5.00	.00	very high
8. I like accessories in performance.	5.00	.00	very high
9. The duration of role plays is suitable.	4.72	.49	high
10. I share feelings with friends during activities.	4.00	.79	high
11. The atmosphere of the classroom is joyful and friendly.	4.18	.70	high
12. I always cooperate in speaking activities	4.41	.64	high
13. I speak more clearly after speaking activities.	5.00	.00	very high
14. I feel more confident than usual.	5.00	.00	very high
15. I like the speaking activities the most.	5.00	.00	very high
Total Average	4.84	.62	high

VI. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

1. According to the research findings, the data collected before applying speaking activities on performance of storytelling and role plays revealed that the students tend to develop their ability on speaking to the highest level or professional level.
2. By using speaking activities on performance of storytelling and role plays, the students enjoy learning activities, participating with friends and teachers, taking advantage from learning and speaking activities, supporting critical thinking, critically thinking for applying their own speaking. Moreover; students' expression can be made significantly, developing speaking skill should be taken continuously as well.
3. The research finding on learning activities on performance of role plays and storytelling, assumed by the satisfaction questionnaire, could influence learning achievement of learners to meet the expectation of speaking skill. In addition, the teacher agreed that the students gained more knowledge and developed their speaking skill, as well as the students revealed that with knowledge of learning activities; they could improve their participation and creative thinking.

VII. RECOMMENDATIONS

Adequate period of time is one of the most important factors affecting and influencing level of development on speaking skill for preschoolers [14]. In addition, taking part in learning activities on speaking of the students increasing the development level because if students participate on learning activities, they tend to be motivated to learn and develop effectively. Accordingly, it is necessary for teachers to adjust teaching style to match and serve the nature and needs of the students, [15] which the researcher discovered that the development of speaking skill on performance activities of storytelling and role plays is an effective approach of improving and developing learning achievement of students.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Cajete, Gregory, Donna Eder, and Regina Holyan. "Life Lessons through Storytelling: Children's Exploration of Ethics", Bloomington: Indiana UP, 2010

- [2] Tuntiplashewa, "Development of speaking at Early age on Performance Activities", Master degree in early childhood education, Srina Karintharawiro
- [3] Aguilar, L.- Machuca, M.J.- Martinez, G.(1991) " Oral Traditions In Storytelling ." Retrieved November 21, 2013.
- [4] Davidson, Michelle (2004). "A phenomenological : using storytelling as a primary teaching method". Nurse Education and Practice 4 (3): 184
- [5] Andrews, Dee; Hull, Donah(Sept.2009). "Storytelling an Instructional Method: Descriptions and Research Question". The Interdisciplinary Journal of Problem-Based Learning. 2 3: 6–23.
- [6] Ball, M.J. (1991) "Connected speech in English: Stress and pitch in conflict", in Proceedings of the ESCA Workshop ' Phonetics and Phonology of Speaking Styles:
- [7] Barry, M.C. (1984) "Connected speech: processes, motivations, models", journal "Cambridge Papers in Phonetics and Experimental Linguistics" September 2 October 1991. pp. 8-1 - 8-10.
- [8] Bergem, D.R. van (1991) "Acoustic and lexical vowel reduction", in Proceedings of the ESCA Workshop ' Phonetics and Phonology of Speaking Styles: Reduction and LLISTERRI, J. (1992)"Speaking styles in speech research", ELSNET/ESCA/SALT Workshop on Integrating Speech and Natural Language. Dublin, Ireland, 15- 17 July 1992.
- [9] Bhatt, P.- LEON, P. (1991) "Melodic patterns in three types of radio discourse", in Proceedings of the ESCA Workshop ' Phonetics and Phonology of Speaking Styles: September - 2 October 1991. pp 11-1 - 11-5
- [10] Blaauw, E. (1991) "Phonetic characteristics of spontaneous and read-aloud speech", in Proceedings of the ESCA Workshop ' Phonetics and Phonology of Speaking Styles:
- [11] CID, M.- Fernandez Corugedo, S.G. (1991) "The construction of a corpus of Speech Communication", in Proceedings of the ESCA Workshop ' Phonetics and Phonology of Speaking Styles: Reduction and Elaboration in . Barcelona, Catalonia, Spain, 30 September - 2 October 1991. p. 17.
- [12] Delgado, M.R.- Freitas, M.J. (1991) "Temporal structures of speech: 'Reading news on TV'", in Proceedings of the ESCA Worksho 'Phonetics and Phonology of Speaking Styles: Reduction and Elaboration in Speech Communication'. Barcelona, Catalonia, Spain, 30 September - 2 October 1991. pp 19-1 -19-5.
- [13] Fant, G.- Kruckenberg, A.- NORD, L. (1991) "Some observations on speaking style in American text reading", in Proceedings of the ESCA Workshop' Phonetics and Phonology of Speaking Styles: 30 September - 2 October 1991. pp. 23-1- 23-5.
- [14] Isolated words and inconnected speech: An investigation of the linguo-mandibular subsystem", in "Speaking styles in speech research , 15-17 July 1992.
- [15] Gregory, M.- Carroll, S. (1978) Language and Situation. Language varieties and their social contexts. London: Routledge & Kegan Paul.

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